

Paper 26

Comparison Analysis of Various CPU Scheduling Algorithms in Operating Systems

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Abstract

Job Scheduling is needed to maintain every computer process that comes with a processor in Parallel Processing Computers. In different conditions, not every algorithm works better on the significant problem. The objective of scheduling is to engage the CPU at its maximum utilization and no process shall not wait for longer time and to finish the entire task in minimum available time. In this paper, we discuss various types of Scheduling algorithms and Compare their performance on terms of throughput and waiting time. FCFS algorithm is better than the other in short burst time while Round Robin is better for multiple processes in every single time. However, it cannot be predicted what process will come after. Average Waiting Time is a standard measure for giving credit to the scheduling algorithm. Several techniques have been applied to maintain the process to make the CPU performance in normal. The objective of this paper is to compare three algorithms, FCFS, SJF, and Round Robin. The target is to know which algorithm is more suitable for the certain process.

Keywords: Process Synchronization, Job Scheduling, FCFS, Preemptive, Non-Preemptive, Round Robin, SJF.

I. SCHEDULING

Scheduling can be defined as a mechanism or a tool to control the execution of number of processes performed by a computer. CPU is the most important of all the resources available in a computer system that are scheduled before use; Multiprogramming is attained by efficient scheduling of the CPU. The basic idea is to keep the CPU busy as much as possible by executing a process, and then switch to another process. The key to Multi- Programming is scheduling. The Multi-Layer Queue (MLQ) scheduling partitions the queue into several Separate queues. Each queue has its own scheduling Algorithm. Each process can be easily classified into Groups based on several properties of the process and permanently assigned to one queue. In the MLFQ scheduling, the processes can be dynamically moved in different queues. So processes that need a large amount of CPU time are sent to the low priority queues and process requiring less amount of CPU and more other bounds are sent to high priority queues. [01]

The Scheduling performance can be analyzed on following criteria:

1. **CPU utilization**:-The maximum use of CPU when it is busy.
2. **Throughput**:- It is the number of processes that complete there execution per unit time.
3. **Turnaround Time**:-It is the amount needed for execution of a single process.
4. **Waiting Time**:- It is the amount of time a process waits in the ready queue.
5. **Response Time**:-This is the amount of time takes from when a request was submitted until the first response is produced not output.

Scheduling can be divided into two categories.

1. **Non preemptive**:- A non preemptive scheduling algorithm picks a process to run and then just lets it run until it blocks or until it voluntarily released by CPU, in other words it engages itself with the first task or job until unless finished, for e.g. FCFS, SJF.
2. **Preemptive**:- in this type of scheduling execution of process may be preempted before the completion of the burst time of process and some other process may starts its execution whose priority is higher than the first arrived process in the CPU, for e.g. Round Robin, Priority Driven.

Let's take 10 processes that arrive at same time in the below given order and analysis their performance in various scheduling (namely FCFS, SJF, RR & Priority) algorithms, with given priorities and time quantum of 9ms.

We have used MATLAB for above analysis and tried to attain maximum possible accurate results.

Process	CPU burst time(ms)	Priority
P1	34	9
P2	23	10

P3	11	8
P4	66	6
P5	21	7
P6	56	5
P7	16	4
P8	9	1
P9	17	3
P10	29	2

FCFS is a non preemptive scheduling algorithm. It uses First in- First out) FIFO strategy to assign the priority to processes in the order, that is same as the request made by process for the processor. The process or job that requests the CPU first is allocated the CPU first and other if in the queue has to wait until the CPU is free. FCFS is also known as First-In-First-Out (FIFO), it is the simplest scheduling methodology. All the later arriving jobs are inserted into the tail (rear) of the ready queue and the process to be executed next is removed from the head (front) of the queue and the control of current process is transferred to the CPU. FCFS gives better performance for longer jobs and less multiple processes in ready queue. Relative importance of jobs measured only by arrival time (poor choice).

Gantt chart for above process as per FCFS is

P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	
0	34	57	68	134	155	211	227	236	253	282

Average waiting time = $1375/10=137.5\text{ms}$
 Turnaround time =burst time +waiting time
 Average turnaround time = $1657/10=165.7\text{ ms}$

Fig 1:-Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Waiting Time for FCFS.

Fig 2:- Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Turnaround Time for FCFS.

Drawback of FIFO can be observed as, the average time for waiting for purely FIFO system is very poor as seen in above diagrams also, *“a process with 9ms as burst time has waiting time of 230ms”* especially for low burst time.

Let's take a case of implementing FIFO in Multitasking system. As we know in a multi-task system, several processes are kept in the main memory and the CPU is kept active to run

a process while the others are waiting. In case of FIFO the multiple tasks will be waiting in the ready queue till the first job is over.

III. SHORTEST JOB FIRST (SJF)

In SJF technique the shortest amongst the entire ready queue job is executed first rest all are preempted. The benefit if this is that waiting time is minimal for the shorter jobs. The SJF is especially appropriate for the batch jobs for which the run time are known in advance. SJF can be classified in two schemes non preemptive and preemptive. **Non preemptive SJF**:- Once the CPU is given to the process it cannot be preempted until it completes its CPU burst, even though if an arriving process has shorter burst time. **Preemptive SJF (SRTF)**:- If a new process arrives to the CPU with shorter burst time than the current executing process then the CPU preempts the currently executing time of current executing process. This scheme

Gantt chart for above process as per Non preemptive SJF is

P8	P3	P7	P9	P5	P2	P10	P1	P6	P4
0	9	20	36	53	74	97	126	160	216
282									

Average waiting time= 791/10=79.1ms

Average turn around time = 1082/10=108.2 ms

Fig 3:- Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Waiting Time for SJF.

Fig 4:- Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Turnaround Time for SJF.

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Gantt chart for above process as per Non preemptive SJF is

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Fig 3:-Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Waiting Time for SJF.

Fig 4:-Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Turnaround Time for SJF.

Drawback of SJF algorithm is to know which incoming process is indeed shorter than another. This requires a separate algorithm running for monitoring and sorting the jobs in real time. Also, long running jobs may starve, because the CPU may have a good and steady supply of short jobs. SJF has two variants, one as always known SJF and the other is LJF (longest Job First) [02].

IV. ROUND ROBIN SCHEDULING

In this approach a fixed time slot is defined before the execution of processes starts, which is a normally small unit of time. In each time slice (quantum) the CPU executes the current process only up to the end of time slice. If that process is having less burst time than the time slice then it is completed and is discarded from the queue and the next process in queue is handled by CPU. However, if the process is not completed then it is halted (preempted) and is put at the end of the queue and then the next process as per arrival time in line is addressed during the next time slice. Round Robin reduces the penalty that short jobs suffer with FCFS by preempting running jobs periodically, and also saves starving of longer jobs and scheduling effort in case of SJF. The main advantage of Round Robin Scheduling is that every process gets the CPU and thus there is no starvation.

Fig 6:- Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Turnaround Time for Round Robin.

For this analysis we have assumed a time quantum of 9ms

Gantt chart:-

P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	
0	9	18	27	36	45	54	63	72	81	90
P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P9	P10	P1	
99	108	110	119	128	137	143	151	160	169	
P2	P4	P5	P6	P10	P1	P4	P6	P10	P4	
174	183	186	195	204	211	220	229	231	240	
P6	P4	P6	P4	P6	P4					
249	258	267	276	278	281					

Average waiting time= 1555/10=155.5ms

Average turnaround time = 1837/10=183.7ms

Fig 5:- Graph representation of The Performance of the Process between Burst Time and Waiting Time for Round Robin.

Drawback of this method is that it slows down the short processes because they have to share the CPU time with other processes instead of just finishing up quickly. Thus the critical issue with the RR policy is the length of the quantum. In case it is too short, then the CPU will be spending more time on context switching or if too long then processes demanding less CPU time will suffer.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have discussed about scheduling and then various types of scheduling. A comparison of various types of algorithms is also shown with practical implementation using

MATLAB. By this experimental setup we have been able to do statistical analysis of the performance of all the four basic scheduling algorithms, as stated above.

REFERENCES

- [01]. Panda, S. K., & Bhoi, S. K. (2014). An effective round robin algorithm using min-max dispersion measure. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1404.5869*.
- [02]. S Panda, S. K., Dash, D., & Rout, J. K. (2014). A group based time quantum round robin algorithm using min-max spread measure. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1403.0335*.
- [03]. Brown, J. E. (2017). On Intelligent Mitigation of Process Starvation In Multilevel Feedback Queue Scheduling.
- [04]. Kadry, S., & Bagdasaryan, A. (2015). New MLFQ Scheduling Algorithm for Operating Systems Using Dynamic quantum. *Statistics, Optimization & Information Computing*, 3(2), 189-196.
- [05]. Banerjee, P., Banerjee, P., & Dhal, S. S. Comparative Performance Analysis of Mid Average Round Robin Scheduling Algorithm (MARR) using Dynamic Time Quantum with Round Robin Scheduling Algorithm having static Time Quantum.